

Collected knowledge on the impacts of agricultural soil management practices in Europe

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Abstract

Soil plays a central role in most aspects of human societies and there is a large body of literature about sustainable soil management. Nevertheless, soil is currently facing degradation arising from different threats, which undermines sustainable development globally. In order to design effective research and policy strategies, it's necessary to identify the current knowledge level about sustainable soil management. This study summarises the key findings from a systematic stocktake of information about agricultural soil management practices in 23 European countries, which included the identification of soil management practices in use, the associated impacts, and the soil challenges addressed. The aim of the study was to understand the current state of knowledge about the impacts of soil management practices, investigated and/or implemented across Europe. The results were analysed at the European level and were also grouped into European Regions and Environmental Zones. Key findings from this study were the identification of knowledge gaps that are key to climate mitigation and adaptation. There is a knowledge gap about soil management practices to avoid greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural soils, as the few reported studies evidence the complexity of the processes governing these emissions. Further knowledge is needed on the impact of tillage practices on long-term carbon storage and distribution along the soil profile, as the reported knowledge was not consensual about carbon storage in deeper soil layers.

Highlights

- Identifying the knowledge about soil management is a key to effective research and policy instruments.
- This study presents the results of a systematic stocktake collected from 23 European countries.
- Further knowledge on practises to avoid greenhouse gas emissions from agricultural soils is needed.
- Knowledge gaps were found in soil challenges that are key to climate mitigation and adaptation.

Keywords: soil management practices, knowledge level, knowledge gaps, soil challenges, soil policy, stocktake, EJPSOIL.

1. Introduction

Soil plays a vital role in nature and there are very different aspects of society that require well-functioning soils (Keesstra et al., 2016). This can be evidenced by the soil's ecosystem functions, a concept that is useful for expressing the value of natural resources to human societies (Glæsner et al., 2014) and that can be divided into four major groups (Weil & Bradley, 2017):

- Provision of food, feed, fibres, wood, and clean water.
- Regulation of the water cycle, nutrient cycles, and the climate.
- Support of biodiversity, human settlements, and primary production of plants.
- Cultural environment for recreation, spiritual uplift, geological, and archaeological archive.

The essential role of soil has been often under-recognized in the European Union's (EU) policy, as evidenced by the lack of a specific regulation tackling the different soil threats, unlike the existing, for several decades, for water, air, and biodiversity (Glæsner et al., 2014; Turpin et al., 2017). But general awareness has been increasing, and soil is presently a priority in research and innovation programs and policies in the EU. Sustainable soil management is a key aspect for current EU policies regarding food, pollution, biodiversity and climate (Montanarella & Panagos, 2021, Panagos et al., 2022). A Soil Strategy for 2030 was adopted, envisioning that all soil ecosystems in the EU will be in a healthy state by 2050. As a contribution to achieve this vision, a proposal for a Directive on Soil Monitoring and Resilience was released in 2030, aiming to achieve healthy soils in the EU in 2050 (European Commission, 2023).

Research on sustainable soil management of agricultural soils is reflected in a wide body of literature. Some examples that can be pointed out are the prevention of soil erosion (Du et al., 2022; Ebabu et al., 2022), the decline of organic matter (Fohrafellner et al., 2022; Gross & Glaser, 2021; Martínez-García et al., 2018), and prevention of soil salinization (Paz et al., 2023a, Cuevas et al., 2019; Daliakopoulos et al., 2016), just to mention three soil threats. However, despite its vital importance, soil is facing degradation globally (FAO, 2015). For example, the average soil erosion rate is higher than soil formation, according to both global and EU estimates (Borrelli et al., 2017, Panagos et al., 2015). In the EU, it is estimated that between 60% and 70% of soils are in unhealthy condition (Veerman et al., 2020). The current unhealthy status of soils can be due to insufficient dissemination of knowledge about sustainable soil management practices, to insufficient incentives to overcome barriers for implementation of these practices, or to a need for further knowledge about the practices and their impacts. If the knowledge level about the impacts of soil management practices on locally relevant soil challenges is high, it may be necessary to promote their further dissemination and implementation. On the contrary, if there are knowledge gaps, further research needs to be supported. In order to design effective research planning and funding strategies, it is important to identify the current knowledge level related to the sustainable management of agricultural soils.

The aim of this study was to collect information about available knowledge on the impacts of agricultural soil management practices across Europe, in order to understand the current knowledge levels and to identify potential knowledge gaps. The study presents the results of systematically collected information by research teams from 23 European countries about the impacts of sustainable soil management practices. According to (FAO, 2017) "Soil management is sustainable if the supporting, provisioning, regulating, and cultural services provided by soil are maintained or enhanced without significantly impairing either the soil functions that enable those services or biodiversity". In order to analyse the knowledge level on sustainable soil management practices, we collected information about practices whose impacts (biophysical, chemical and socio-economic) have been demonstrated either in scientific literature, knowledge repositories or in other sources of knowledge. The results presented in this study contribute to understand the

current state of knowledge and to identify the knowledge gaps about the impacts of agricultural soil management practices in Europe. These results also contributed to develop the roadmap of relevant research and complementary activities to be carried out by the European Joint Programme on Agricultural Soil (EJP SOIL) (Keesstra, S., 2021).

2. Material and methods

The data for this study was collected by means of a questionnaire distributed to 24 research teams, working with agricultural soils in 23 European countries. The research teams integrate the consortium of EJP SOIL and are described in Supplementary Material Table SM1. Each research team compiled information on the sustainable soil management practices investigated and/or implemented in their country by consulting national scientific databases, knowledge repositories and stakeholders, according to their specific contexts. The questionnaires were completed during the second semester of 2020. In order to analyse the geographical context of the reported knowledge, the results were analysed according to European Regions, defined as:

- Northern Europe (Denmark, Norway, Sweden, and Finland)
- Central Europe (Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, Germany, Hungary, Slovakia, Slovenia, Poland, Lithuania, Latvia, and Switzerland)
- Western Europe (Belgium, France, Netherlands, and United Kingdom)
- Southern Europe (Portugal, Spain, Italy, and Turkey)

The impacts of soil management practices are likely to be related to the specific pedo-climatic conditions, which frame soil management in different natural contexts. In order to assess the influence of these natural conditions, the data was additionally analysed according to Environmental Zones. The Environmental Zones classification is a result of the twenty most significant environmental variables, obtained from a Principal Component Analysis, which produced thirteen environmental zones for Europe, according to Figure 1 (Metzger et al., 2005). This study included information collected from 13 Environmental Zones: Alpine North (ALN); Boreal (BOR); Nemoral (NEM); Atlantic North (ATN); Alpine South (ALS); Continental (CON); Atlantic Central (ATC); Pannonian (PAN); Lusitanian (LUS); Anatolian (ANA); Mediterranean Mountains (MDM); Mediterranean North (MDN); Mediterranean South (MDS).

In the questionnaire, the research teams could choose among a total of 30 predefined sustainable soil management practices, which were divided into four management groups, as presented in Table 1. If needed, the teams could specify other practices within each management group. For each reported practice, the teams were asked to identify most important impacts (up to three impacts) and their corresponding Environmental Zone(s). The impacts could be described as positive, negative, or neutral. In order to harmonise the identification of the impacts, the teams chose among 11 impact categories, which include biophysical, chemical, and socio-economic, as detailed in Table 2. The positive impacts were related to a soil management challenge, according to the soil challenges defined by Keesstra et al. (2021), presented in Table 3. In the present work, only the practices with positive impacts were related to the soil challenges, because the aim was to identify knowledge about sustainable soil management practices that contribute to overcome the soil challenges. Finally, the research teams were also asked to identify the most important soil challenges in the Environmental Zones of their country. The data collected in this study is publicly available in Paz et al., (2023b).

Figure 2 presents a scheme of the data that research teams were asked to report: soil management practices were reported for specific Environmental Zones and may have several associated impacts (up to three positive, negative or neutral impacts). Each positive impact is related to a soil challenge.

Table 1. List of predefined sustainable soil management practices for each management group, as presented in the questionnaire

Soil tillage and cover	Crop and cropping system	Nutrient management and crop protection	Water management
No til	Crop rotations	Use of organic fertilizers (green- and animal manure, organic by-products and crop residues, biochar, compost)	Determination of the Water Use Efficiency (photosynthetic WUE, WUE of productivity, water footprint)
Direct seeding	Associations/intercropping/multiple cropping/sequential crop	Use of biofertilizers (biostimulants, nitrogen-fixing microorganisms, mycorrhizae)	Efficient irrigation systems (drippers or micro-sprinklers, subterranean irrigation, distribution efficiency)
Non-inversion/reduced tillage	Cover/catch crops	Use of soil amendments for buffer capacity and pH (organic, inorganic)	Irrigation scheduling (based on models for water and solute transport, soil water balance, water deficit irrigation)
Contour ploughing	Use grassland/ pasture with legumes	Methods for efficient fertilisation (fertiliser recommendation, models to estimate soil nutrient balance)	Drainage systems, management of water table and flooding
Terrace farming	Perennial crops	Mechanical weeding	Monitoring of soil salinisation
Controlled traffic farming	Mulching	Precision of herbicide application	Monitor the quality of irrigation water (for salts, nutrients and potential harmful substances)
Low pressure in tires	Permanent soil cover	Other (specify)	Improve water storage capacity, infiltration and reduction of runoff
Reduction of soil compaction	Vegetated/grass buffer strips		Other (specify)
Other (specify)	Hedges		
	Other (specify)		

Table 2. List of impacts of sustainable soil management practices

Impact categories of soil management practices

Adaptation to climate change
Carbon storage in the soil
Desertification
Farmers profitability
Nutrient in the soil
Other biophysical
Other socio-economic
Readiness for farmer's use
Soil biodiversity
Soil quality
Soil structure

Table 3. List of soil challenges considered in EJP SOIL

Soil challenges

Avoid acidification
Avoid contamination
Avoid N₂O and CH₄ emissions from soils
Avoid peat degradation
Avoid salinisation and alkalinisation
Avoid soil erosion
Avoid soil sealing
Enhance soil biodiversity
Enhance soil nutrient use efficiency
Enhance water storage capacity
Improve soil structure
Maintain/increase soil organic carbon

Figure 1. Map of the Environmental Zones of Europe. Source: (Metzger, 2018).

Figure 2. Scheme of the collected knowledge about sustainable soil management across Europe. Each report comprises the identification of the Environmental Zone(s), soil management practice(s), their impact(s), and related soil challenges.

3. Results

3.1 Knowledge at European level

This section presents the results at the European level, which includes the information reported by all the 23 participating countries. In total, information on 1078 impacts of soil management practices was collected in this stocktake. The distribution of reported knowledge by the four management groups shows that the group “Crops and Cropping Systems” had the largest share with 35% of reports and “Water Management” had the lowest share with 15% (Figure 3).

Analysing the knowledge for each soil management practice, Figure 4 shows the number of the reports for each practice (represented with the same colour for management groups, as in Figure 3). The practice with the most reported knowledge was the “Use of organic fertilisers”. The practices related to soil tillage (“No till”, “Direct seeding”, and “Reduced tillage”) gathered a very high level of reported knowledge. “Crop rotations” and “Cover/catch crops” were the other two soil management practices with very high reported knowledge.

Regarding the impacts of the soil management practices, Figure 5 shows the total amount of positive and negative impacts. The bar colours represent the management groups of the soil management practices associated with each impact, using the colours presented in Figure 3. Considering the positive impacts, Figure 5 shows that there is a high level of knowledge related to practices with positive impacts on “Soil quality”, followed by “Nutrients in the soil”, “Soil structure”, “Carbon storage in the soil”, and “Farmer’s profitability”. Practices in the “Soil Tillage and Cover” group contribute the most to the impact “Soil quality” and to “Soil structure”. Practices in “Crops and cropping systems” group contribute the most to “Carbon storage in the soil”. It can also be pointed out that practices in the “Water management” group contribute the most to the impact “Adaptation to climate change”, evidencing the dominance of practices related mainly to irrigation in the current knowledge about climate change adaptation. The impact with lowest reported knowledge was “Desertification”.

There were comparatively fewer negative impacts reported than positive, as shown in Figure 5. “Farmer’s profitability” and “Carbon storage in the soil” collected the most negative reports, both mainly related to practices in the “Soil tillage and cover” group. There were also three neutral impacts reported regarding the impact “Carbon storage in the soil”, associated with the practices of “No till”, “Reduced till”, and “Direct seeding” (not shown in the figure).

The soil challenges related to the positive impacts of soil management practices are shown in Figures 6 and 7. Figure 6 shows that most of the reported knowledge was related to the challenges of “Enhance soil and nutrient use efficiency”, followed by “Maintain/increase soil organic carbon”, and “Improve soil structure”, indicating a high level of knowledge regarding practices that positively contribute to these challenges. On the other hand, “Avoid acidification” and “Avoid salinization/alkalinisation” were the challenges with least reported knowledge, which can be due to a geographically limited importance of these challenges. Although, despite its wide geographical relevance, “Avoid N₂O and CH₄ emissions”, had a very low level of reported knowledge. The three challenges with largest reported knowledge are among those identified as “most important” by the research teams (see section 2), as shown in Figure 7. The largest relative gaps between reported importance and reported knowledge occurred for the challenges “Avoid acidification” and “Avoid N₂O and CH₄ emissions”, followed by “Avoid soil erosion”. These results can be indicators of relevant knowledge gaps related to these soil challenges, as the percentage of reported knowledge is considerably less than their reported importance.

Figure 3. Relative distribution of the knowledge reported for each management group at European level.

Figure 4. Knowledge reported for soil management practices at European level. The colours of the bars refer to the practices' management groups, using the colour code presented in Figure 3. For sake of reading, the figure displays shortened versions of the practices' full denomination (Table 1).

Figure 5. Positive and negative impacts of soil management practices reported at European level. The colours in the bars indicate the management groups of the soil management practices associated with the impact, using the colour code presented in Figure 3.

Figure 6. Relative share of soil challenges related to soil management practices with positive impacts, as reported at the European level.

Figure 7. Share of soil challenges identified as “most important” by the reporting research teams and the share of reported knowledge associated to each challenge.

3.2 Knowledge by European Regions

In this section, the results are analysed according to European Regions. European Regions are composed of a varying number of countries (as defined in section 2), consequently, there was a varying number of research teams reporting within each region. For this reason, the results are presented in relative frequency of the reported knowledge for each European Region, instead of total reports (as it was the case in the analysis at the European level presented in section 3.1). The total reported impacts included 165 from Northern Europe, 352 from Central Europe, 331 from Western Europe, and 230 from Southern Europe.

The relative importance of management groups among European Regions can be analysed in Figure 8. The figure shows that relatively different levels of knowledge can be observed between regions: in Northern Europe, most knowledge was reported for impacts of practices in the group “Soil tillage and plant cover”, in the Central and Western Europe, most knowledge was reported for the group “Crop and cropping systems”, and in the Southern Region, “Water Management” was the most reported group.

Figure 9 shows the relative distribution of knowledge about the positive and negative impacts of soil management practices. Regarding the positive impacts, Figure 9 shows that all regions reported knowledge about most of the impacts. The exceptions were “Desertification”, which was only reported in Southern Europe and very marginally in Central Europe, and “Readiness for use”, which was not reported in the Northern and Southern European regions. Knowledge about “Carbon storage in the soil” was reported less frequently in Northern Europe, and “Soil Structure” was reported more frequently in this region. Knowledge about “Adaptation to climate change” was relatively more reported in Southern Europe. Regarding the negative impacts (Figure 9b), the reported knowledge focused mainly on “Farmers profitability” (reported for all regions), and

“Carbon storage in the soil”. Under the category “Other biophysical”, negative impacts of some soil practices in the above ground biodiversity and in water bodies were reported.

The soil challenges addressed by the soil management practices with positive impacts are shown in Figure 10, with their relative frequency for each European Region. Most challenges were reported for every region, but some variability was observed. For example, “Improve soil structure” was reported more frequently in Northern Europe than in Southern Europe. “Maintain/ increase soil organic carbon” was reported more frequently in Central Europe, and “Enhance soil biodiversity” was reported more frequently in Western Europe. Knowledge related to the challenge “Avoid salinisation and alkalinisation” was only reported in Western and Southern Europe, which can result from regional concerns associated with irrigation management practices and climate conditions. Knowledge related to “Avoid acidification” is only reported in Central and Western Europe, which points to concerns about acidification effects in these regions. “Avoid N₂O and CH₄ emissions from soils” was not reported in the Northern Europe.

Figure 8. Relative distribution of reported knowledge about soil management practices (grouped into four management groups) for each European region.

Figure 9. Relative distribution of knowledge about positive and negative impacts of soil management practices in each European.

Figure 10. Relative distribution of soil challenges associated with soil management practices in each European region.

3.3 Knowledge by Environmental Zones

In this section, the results are analysed according to the 13 Environmental Zones, as defined in section 2. As the countries have a varying number of Environmental Zones, the results were analysed as relative frequency. Figure 11 shows the relative distribution of knowledge on soil management practices, grouped into the four management groups, for each Environmental Zone. Figure 11 shows that knowledge about practices from the four management groups has been reported for all Environmental Zones with the exception of “Water management”, which is not reported in MDM. Even if there was some variation in the representativeness of the management groups between different zones, it was difficult to identify clear patterns related to the Environmental Zones.

Figure 12 shows the relative distribution of knowledge reported on the positive (a) and negative (b) impacts of soil management practices for the different Environmental Zones. Most of the impacts collected positive reports for all Environmental Zones (Figure 12a), which points to a transversal level of knowledge about those impacts. Exceptions occur for “Desertification” which is the most asymmetrically reported impact, occurring only in MDS and PAN and “Readiness for use” which had few reports, and only in half of the Environmental Zones. Regarding the negative impacts, Figure 12b shows that “Carbon storage in the soil” and “Farmer’s profitability” dominated the negative impacts in many Environmental Zones, mainly due to reported negative impacts of reduced soil tillage practices in “Carbon storage in the soil” and on “farmer’s profitability” (as shown in Figure 5).

The soil challenges related to the soil management practices with positive impacts, for each Environmental Zone are shown in Figure 13. In general, the challenges were reported in comparable proportions for most Environmental Zones, but the less reported challenges were not reported for all Environmental Zones. For instance, “Avoid acidification” was only reported in ATC and CON, while “Avoid salinisation and alkalinisation” was not reported in half of the Environmental Zones (ALS, BOR, CON, LUS, NEM and PAN), which is likely due to varying knowledge levels according to different soil challenges in the Environmental Zones.

Figure 11. Relative distribution of reported knowledge about soil management practices (grouped into four management groups) for each Environmental Zones: Alpine North (ALN); Boreal (BOR); Nemoral (NEM); Atlantic North (ATN); Alpine South (ALS); Continental (CON); Atlantic Central (ATC); Pannonian (PAN); Lusitanian (LUS); Anatolian (ANA); Mediterranean Mountains (MDM); Mediterranean North (MDN); Mediterranean South (MDS).

Figure 12. Relative distribution of reported knowledge about the a) positive impacts and b) negative impacts of soil management practices in the different Environmental Zones.

Figure13. Relative distribution of reported knowledge related to each soil challenge per Environmental Zone.

4. Discussion

4.1. Knowledge on impacts of soil management practices at European level

The practice with the most reported knowledge was the “Use of organic fertilisers”, with positive impacts on “Carbon storage in the soil”, “Soil biodiversity”, and “Nutrients in the soil”. This result points out to a high interest in this practice in the current scientific research and likely a widening interest in its implementation, as it is currently applied in a minority of the agricultural areas in Europe.

Practices related to soil tillage (“No till”, “Direct seeding”, and “Reduced tillage”) had a very high level of reported knowledge. This set of practices had positive impacts mainly in “Soil structure”, followed by “Soil biodiversity”, “Soil quality”, “Nutrients in the soil”, and “Adaptation to climate change”. Neutral and negative impacts of these practices on “Carbon storage in the soil” were reported. This indicates that practices related to reduced soil tillage are recognized as having multiple positive impacts on the soil. Although, the reported studies pointed to benefits mainly to the top soil layers (e.g. González-Sánchez et al., 2012; Martins et al., 2011; Mazzoncini et al., 2011; Morugán-Coronado et al., 2020). In deeper soil layers, different studies concluded that there were no significant differences, or even significant decreases in carbon concentration with depth (e.g. Dimassi et al., 2014; Hansen et al., 2015; Powlson et al., 2014; Shrestha et al., 2015).

“Crop rotations” and “Cover/catch crops” were the other two soil management practices with very high reported knowledge and with positive impacts on “Carbon storage in the soil”, “Soil structure”, “Soil biodiversity”, “Soil quality”, “Nutrients in the soil”, “Farmer’s profitability”, and “Adaptation to climate change”. In the case of “Cover/catch crops”, the high level of reported knowledge can be related to their inclusion as greening measures in the Common Agricultural Policy (2014-2020) and in the Rural Development Plans of several Member States (Kathage et al., 2022).

The impact “Desertification” had a low level of reported knowledge, which could be partially explained because it is a cross-cutting impact, resulting from a set of degradation processes associated with other impacts (Egidi et al., 2021). Even so, the results indicate that few studies are conducted with an integrated view of the degradation processes involved in desertification in

the several European contexts. This result is of major importance because desertification is a growing threat in the EU, and it was estimated that 25% of land in Southern, Central and Eastern Europe face high or very high risk of desertification (European Court of Auditors, 2018; Právělie et al., 2017). Desertification has drastic consequences for soil functions, can be irreversible, and is expected to exacerbate with climate change (Burrell et al., 2020). To combat desertification, knowledge on the impacts of practices within crops and cropping systems and soil tillage and cover, such as the use of perennial crops with natural or sown soil cover, diversified and locally adapted agricultural and agroforestry systems, permanent pastures, and reduced tillage, could be of main importance.

Practices to avoid N₂O and CH₄ emissions soils had a very low level of reported knowledge. This was also found in recent studies about the impacts of soil management practices (Heller, et. al. n.d.). Furthermore, some of the reported studies showed contradictory results, highlighting the complexity and low level of knowledge about those processes (Alluvione et al., 2010; Sandén et al., 2018; Struck et al., 2020). This can be due to the fact that emission reduction has not been a priority for farmers, agronomists, and researchers, as it was outside the long-established goals of agriculture, and indicates a clear need for further research and/or dissemination of practices addressing this challenge. There is the need for knowledge about the impacts of several practices on soil greenhouse gas emissions, such as the inclusion of legumes in rotations, tillage methods, rice cultivation practices, and practices for improved soil microbiome. Emissions of N₂O and CH₄ from soils are about 31% of the EU agricultural emissions, representing a relatively important option for decreasing greenhouse gas emissions in the EU (EEA, 2023).

There was a low level of reported negative impacts of soil management practices. It is possible that there was an underrepresentation of negative impacts of soil management practices, as these are often not the focus of the studies and might be highly context-dependent. This potential bias was also found in other studies attempting to collect information about the impact of soil management practices with expert questionnaires (Heller, et. al n.d.). Among the negative impacts, there were relatively more negative reports on the impact “Farmers’ profitability”, which indicates the need for further support for the dissemination of sustainable soil management practices. Eventually, additional incentives at the national/regional/EU level would help farmers to adopt these practices.

Even though most reported knowledge on adaptation to climate change is related to “Water management” practices, a broader set of sustainable soil management practices, including practices related to crops and cropping systems and soil tillage and cover, must be mastered in order to adapt to the changing climate conditions.

Regarding the soil challenges, large gaps were observed between the attributed importance and the reported knowledge in some soil challenges, namely “Avoid N₂O and CH₄ emissions”, “Avoid soil erosion”, and “Avoid acidification”. This indicates the need for further knowledge or dissemination of soil management practices related to these challenges. “Maintain/increase soil organic carbon” and “Avoid soil erosion” were the priority soil challenges for the research teams consulted in the current study. In a recent study, resulting from the consultation of a range of stakeholders in European countries, “Maintain/increase soil organic carbon” was also identified as the priority challenge, although there was a rather different ranking of importance in the following soil challenges (Vanino et al., 2023).

4.2. Main difference among European Regions

The variations between reported knowledge between European Region are likely related to different concerns and needs regarding soil challenges at the regional level. An example are practices in the “Water management” group, namely “Efficient irrigation” and “Irrigation schedule”,

which relatively more reported in Southern Europe, due to the limitations in the availability of rainwater for crop production. Although, knowledge on irrigation and water use efficiency was reported in all European Regions, with several countries in Western Europe identifying a high level of knowledge on practices in this group. On the other hand, practices to “Avoid N₂O and CH₄ emissions from soils” was not reported in the Northern Europe, despite the transversal relevance of avoiding greenhouse gas emissions from soils, as reduction of greenhouse gases is an objective in European countries included in this study.

Regarding practices related to soil tillage, “No till” gathered more knowledge in Southern Europe, while in other regions “Reduced till” was most reported, which might result from the adequation of soil minimum tillage practices to soils with different structures and under different climatic conditions. Knowledge related to the practices impacts on soil structure was relatively more reported in Northern Europe, while knowledge related to maintaining and increasing carbon in the soil was relatively less reported than in other regions, which points to the lower relevance of this issue in the agricultural soils of this region when compared to the soils of regions with lower soil organic carbon.

In Southern Europe, “Adaptation to climate change” was relatively more reported, which can be explained by the limiting climate conditions for agricultural production and to an earlier experience of climate change in this region, as atmospheric warming in Mediterranean countries has exceeded global average rates (IPCC), 2023).

4.3 Main difference among Environmental Zones

It was not straightforward to define patterns of different knowledge level according to the Environmental Zones, as most of the impacts were reported for all Environmental Zones in a significant proportion, which points to a rather transversal level of knowledge about those impacts, when aggregated at this level. Desertification was the impact with most asymmetrical knowledge among Environmental Zones, reported only in MDS and PAN. This is rather surprising as the risk of desertification occurs in other Environmental Zones in Europe, such as MDN and MDM (Právělie et al., 2017).

The current synthesis provides a view about the knowledge level and knowledge gaps on the impacts of soil management practices. Despite the attempt to harmonize the collected information, the synthesis can present biases due to the particular perspectives of reporting teams, or to other general biases in the build-up of knowledge, as discussed in the following section. The current study does not attempt to provide a meta-analysis on the impacts of soil management practices, but the collected references can serve as a base for such studies.

5. Conclusions

This study collected and evaluated knowledge about the impacts of agricultural soil management practices in Europe, resulting from the assessment carried out by 24 research teams in 23 European countries. The results allowed to identify the knowledge level about the impacts of sustainable soil management practices and the related soil challenges and to identify knowledge gaps. The main findings were related to the identification of knowledge gaps, namely:

- There is a knowledge gap about practices for avoiding N₂O and CH₄ emissions from agricultural soils. The few reported studies evidence the complexity and context-dependency of the processes governing such emissions.
- There are large relative gaps between the reported importance and the reported knowledge on “Avoid acidification” and “Avoid soil erosion”, indicating the need for

further knowledge or dissemination of soil management practices related to these challenges.

- Further knowledge is needed on the impacts of tillage practices on carbon storage in the soil, including long-term experiments in both topsoil and deeper soil layers, in order to achieve a more comprehensive understanding of the vertical dynamics of carbon in the soil under such management practices, in different environmental zones and agricultural systems.
- Desertification had a very low level of reported knowledge, indicating that few studies are conducted with an integrated view of the degradation processes involved in desertification in the different European contexts, where desertification is a growing threat.

The study identified knowledge gaps that are key to climate change mitigation and adaptation. The results suggest that these knowledge gaps should be in focus when designing strategies for research funding and knowledge dissemination, in order to meet the goal of climate-smart management of agricultural soil.

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Supplementary Material:

Table SM1: Institutions and countries of the research teams contributing to the knowledge reported in this study.

Data availability:

The data supporting this study is publicly available in the permanent repository ZENODO at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10091784>

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